

Oxidative Addition and Adduct Formation Reaction of Carbonyl Compounds of Rhodium(I)

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Rhodium(I) carbonyl complexes of the type $trans-[RhCl(CO)(R_2SO/R_2S)_2]$, where R_2SO = di-n-propyl sulphoxide (n-Pr₂SO), di-n-butyl sulphoxide (n-Bu₂SO); R_2S = dimethyl sulphide (Me₂S), di-isopropyl sulphide (i-Pr₂S), undergo oxidative addition reactions with small covalent molecules (YZ) forming the adducts $[RhClYZ(CO)(R_2SO/R_2S)_2]$, where $YZ = Cl_2, Br_2, I_2, ICl$ and tetracyanoethylene (TCNE). With CH_3I , rhodium(I) compounds form a mixture of six- and five-coordinate acetyl derivatives. During oxidation, R_2SO ligands undergo isomeric rearrangement forming metal-oxygen bonded R_2SO complexes.

In recent years oxidative addition reactions (OA) of transitions metal complexes have gained much importance because of their use in hydrogenation and hydroformylation reactions¹⁻⁵. Many square-planar complexes of platinum group metals, particularly low-spin d^8 -ions, undergo OA reactions with small molecules such as O_2, H_2, CH_3I , halogen, ICl etc. producing six-coordinate species in which the central metal ions possess the d^6 -configuration. Rh^I and Ir^I complexes readily undergo OA reactions⁶⁻⁸. The conversion of the square-planar $trans-[RhX(CO)L_2]$ to octahedral complexes, $[RhXYZ(CO)L_2]$, where $X = Cl^-, Br^-$; $YZ = Cl_2, Br_2, I_2, ICl, CH_3I$; $L = PPh_3, AsPh_3, SbPh_3$ and $(C_2H_5)_2S$, have been reported⁹⁻¹⁴. Moreover, d^8 -platinum group metals, particularly Rh^I and Ir^I carbonyl compounds, show a considerable tendency to form adducts with a number of neutral donor molecules such as SO_2 and $TCNE$ ¹⁵⁻¹⁹. In the present study, the OA reactions of complexes $trans-[RhCl(CO)(R_2SO/R_2S)_2]$ (1)²⁰, where $R_2SO = n-Pr_2SO, n-Bu_2SO$; $R_2S = Me_2S, i-Pr_2S$, with Cl_2, Br_2, I_2, ICl , or CH_3I and adduct formation of 1 with $TCNE$, are reported.

Experimental

$RhCl_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ (Johnson Matthey), and di-n-propyl sulphoxide, di-n-butyl sulphoxide, dimethyl sulphide and di-isopropyl sulphide (all Aldrich) were used as such. Bromine, iodine monochloride, methyl iodide and tetracyanoethylene were of A.R. grade (Riedel). All the solvents were purified by the usual procedures before use.

$trans-[RhCl(CO)(R_2SO/R_2S)_2]$ ($R_2SO = n-Pr_2SO, n-Bu_2SO$; $R_2S = Me_2S, i-Pr_2S$) was prepared as

described earlier²⁰ by treating the chlorobridge carbonyl compound $[Rh(CO)_2Cl]_2$ with appropriate ligands. The oxidative addition products, $[RhClYZ(CO)(R_2SO/R_2S)_2]$, where $YZ = Cl_2, Br_2, I_2, ICl$ and CH_3I , were prepared by the following general method.

Compound 1 was dissolved in chloroform and a saturated solution of Cl_2 in carbon tetrachloride was added. Br_2, I_2 or ICl dissolved in chloroform were added in stoichiometric amounts (1 : 1 molar ratio). The solutions were kept in a desiccator over $CaCl_2$ under N_2 for a few hours in a refrigerator at 0°. After evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure, the desired product separated out as fine crystalline powder was washed with a minimum volume of diethyl ether. CH_3I was added directly to 1, and the resulting solution was set aside for 3-4 h in a desiccator in a refrigerator. The concentrated solution was again treated with CH_3I and set aside for 2 h. After evaporating the solvent slowly under reduced pressure, the desired product separated out as slightly pasty mass was washed with a minimum volume of diethyl ether and dried over P_2O_5 in a desiccator.

The $TCNE$ adducts of the parent compounds containing R_2SO could not be isolated because they decomposed. The adducts, $[RhCl(CO)(Me_2S/i-Pr_2S)_2TCNE]$ could, however, be prepared as follows. $trans-[RhCl(CO)(Me_2S/i-Pr_2S)_2]$ was dissolved in benzene and to it a stoichiometric amount (1 : 1 molar ratio) of a freshly prepared solution of $TCNE$ in benzene was added with constant stirring. The solution was set aside overnight to permit completion of the reaction. On evaporating the solvent under reduced pressure, the corresponding compound separated out as shining yellow

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crystals which were then washed with benzene and dried over P₂O₅ in a desiccator (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

Infrared spectra : The carbonyl stretching bands (1 950–2 025 cm⁻¹) for all the *trans*- [RhCl(CO)(R₂SO/R₂S)₂] complexes shifted to higher values (2 055–2 110 cm⁻¹) when YZ were added oxidatively (Table 2). Similar trend in ν_{CO} values has also been reported earlier^{5,9,10,11,14,17}. It is interesting to note that in the square-planar complexes *trans*- [RhX(CO)(R₂SO/R₂S)₂] (X=Cl⁻, Br⁻), the ν_{CO} values increases²⁰ in the order, Br > Cl, but in [RhClYZ(CO)(R₂SO/R₂S)₂] complexes a reverse trend is observed (YZ=Cl₂, Br₂ and I₂). The value for the ν_{CO} band of [RhCl₂I(CO)(R₂SO/R₂S)₂] lies in between the ν_{CO} values for [RhCl₂(CO)(R₂SO/R₂S)₂] and [RhClI₂(R₂SO/R₂S)₂]. All these observations can be rationalised on the basis of arguments developed earlier^{14,17,19}.

The OA reaction of CH₃I with **1** is interesting because CH₃I is expected to form first a six-coordinate complex which rearranges to an acetyl derivative. This internal conversion results in the reduction of the coordination number of the central metal ion from six to five¹⁹. It has been found that CH₃I reacts with **1** to form a mixture of two different compounds, namely, [RhClI(CH₃CO)(R₂SO/R₂S)₂] and [RhClI(COCH₃)(R₂SO/R₂S)₂], which could not be separated. The formation of these two different types of complexes is evident from the carbonyl stretching frequencies of the complexes – the terminal CO group in [RhClI(CH₃CO)(R₂SO/R₂S)₂] absorbs in the region 2 050 cm⁻¹ while in the five-coordinate complex, [RhClI(COCH₃)(R₂SO/R₂S)₂], ν_{CO} occurs at 1 720 cm⁻¹ (split bands in nujol). This band corresponds to the carbonyl stretching frequency of an acyl ligand.

In the square-planar complex, [RhCl(CO)(R₂SO)₂], R₂SO molecules are bonded to the metal ion through sulphur donors only²⁰ as is evident from ν_{SO} band at ~1 100 cm⁻¹. Upon OA reactions with YZ, the ν_{SO} band at ~1 100 cm⁻¹ almost disappears and a new band appears near

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL DATA AND COLOUR OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
		Rh	Halogen
[RhCl ₂ (CO)(n-Pr ₂ SO) ₂]	Yellow	20.28 (20.35)	21.02 (21.04)
[RhClBr ₂ (CO)(n-Pr ₂ SO) ₂]	Brown	17.52 (17.31)	32.21 (32.85)
[RhClI ₂ (CO)(n-Pr ₂ SO) ₂]	Blackish brown	14.71 (14.94)	42.05 (42.01)
[RhCl ₂ I(CO)(n-Pr ₂ SO) ₂]	Brown	17.56 (17.24)	33.81 (33.13)
[RhClI(CH ₃ CO)(n-Pr ₂ SO) ₂]	Brown	17.21 (17.84)	28.94 (28.16)
[RhCl ₂ (CO)(n-Bu ₂ SO) ₂]	Brown	18.21 (18.92)	18.79 (18.94)
[RhClBr ₂ (CO)(n-Bu ₂ SO) ₂]	Deep brown	15.71 (15.82)	30.91 (30.02)
[RhClI ₂ (CO)(n-Bu ₂ SO) ₂]	Blackish brown	13.62 (13.82)	38.85 (38.86)
[RhCl ₂ I(CO)(n-Bu ₂ SO) ₂]	Brown	15.75 (15.75)	30.42 (30.29)
[RhClI(CH ₃ CO)(n-Bu ₂ SO) ₂]	Deep brown	16.01 (16.26)	25.31 (25.66)
[RhCl ₂ (CO)(Me ₂ S) ₂]	Brown	28.32 (28.47)	28.96 (29.42)
[RhClBr ₂ (CO)(Me ₂ S) ₂]	Brownish red	22.48 (22.85)	43.41 (43.36)
[RhClI ₂ (CO)(Me ₂ S) ₂]	Reddish brown	18.82 (18.90)	53.28 (53.14)
[RhCl ₂ I(CO)(Me ₂ S) ₂]	Reddish brown	22.61 (22.72)	43.11 (43.67)
[RhClI(CH ₃ CO)(Me ₂ S) ₂]	Deep brown	23.61 (23.79)	37.21 (37.54)
[RhCl ₂ (CO)(i-Pr ₂ S) ₂]	Brown	21.63 (21.78)	22.12 (22.46)
[RhClBr ₂ (CO)(i-Pr ₂ S) ₂]	Brown	18.12 (18.29)	34.34 (34.72)
[RhClI ₂ (CO)(i-Pr ₂ S) ₂]	Blackish brown	15.43 (15.67)	44.18 (44.06)
[RhCl ₂ I(CO)(i-Pr ₂ S) ₂]	Brown	18.32 (18.21)	34.98 (35.01)
[RhClI(CH ₃ CO)(i-Pr ₂ S) ₂]	Brown	18.63 (18.89)	29.72 (29.81)
[RhCl(CO)(Me ₂ S) ₂ TCNE]	Yellow	24.21 (24.59)	8.31 (8.48)
[RhCl(CO)(i-Pr ₂ S) ₂ TCNE]	Yellow	19.02 (19.39)	6.29 (6.69)

TABLE 2—ν_{CO} AND ν_{SO} STRETCHING FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF COMPLEXES

Parent compd.	ν _{CO} (ν _{SO}) cm ⁻¹	Oxidised products, ν _{CO} (ν _{SO}) cm ⁻¹										ν _{CO} (cm ⁻¹) TCNE adducts (nujol)
		Cl ₂		Br ₂		I ₂		ICl		OH ₂ I		
		Nujol	OHCl ₂	Nujol	OHCl ₂	Nujol	OHCl ₂	Nujol	OHCl ₂	Nujol	OHCl ₂	
[RhCl(CO)(n-Pr ₂ SO) ₂]	2 022 (1 122, 1 112)	2 092 (920m)	—	2 086 (930s)	2 098	2 072 (928s)	2 080	2 060 (935s)	2 090	2 056 1 720m ^a (940s)	2 068 1 712m	Decomposed
[RhCl(CO)(n-Bu ₂ SO) ₂]	2 020 (1 120, 1 110)	2 098 (920m)	—	2 090 (925s)	2 105	2 075 (930s)	2 082	2 075 (930s)	2 088	2 052 1 705m ^a (1 220vw, 940s)	2 064 1 710m	Decomposed
[RhCl(CO)(Me ₂ S) ₂]	1 972	2 096	—	2 080	2 096	2 072	2 080	2 080	2 090	2 062 1 712m ^a	2 070 1 716m	2 088 (2 230s) ^b
[RhCl(CO)(i-Pr ₂ S) ₂]	1 950	2 108	—	2 080	2 092	2 078	2 090	2 082	2 088	2 050 1 710m ^a	2 068 1 710w	2 085 (2 230s) ^b

^aSplit. ^bν_{CN} in nujol.

935 cm^{-1} which is the characteristic for ν_{SO} when the R_2SO ligand is bonded to the metal through its oxygen donor. In the parent compound **1**, the 'softer' sulphur atom in the R_2SO molecule tends to combine with the 'soft' Rh^{I} ion, but in the oxidised product the central metal ion is 'harder' and prefers to bind with the 'harder' oxygen atom of the R_2SO ligand. Thus, on the basis of the concept of 'hard-hard' interaction²¹, it is probable that during the formation of $[\text{RhClYZ}(\text{CO})(\text{R}_2\text{SO})_2]$, R_2SO ligands undergo rearrangement to facilitate the formation of $\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}-\text{O}$ bonds.

The TCNE adducts, $[\text{RhCl}(\text{CO})(\text{R}_2\text{S})_2\text{TCNE}]$ are stable in air and are soluble in most common organic solvents. All the adducts exhibit medium to strong stretching bands in the region 2200–2240 cm^{-1} which are indicative of the presence of a coordinately bonded TCNE group. Depending upon the increase in ν_{CO} values, the adducts, $[\text{RhCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2\text{TCNE}]$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$, AsPh_3 and SbPh_3), are known to exist¹⁹ as five-coordinate species with tetragonal pyramidal structure (A), the apex of which is occupied by the TCNE group or as six-coordinated quasi-octahedral structure (B). In the structure (A), the metal ion formally exist in +1 oxidation state and in the structure (B), in +3 state. For the planar complex, $[\text{RhCl}(\text{CO})(\text{R}_2\text{S})_2]$, ν_{CO}

Structure (A)

Structure (B)

occurs near 1970 cm^{-1} while the adduct, $[\text{RhCl}(\text{CO})(\text{R}_2\text{S})_2\text{TCNE}]$ displays bands near 2080 cm^{-1} which is about 110 cm^{-1} higher than in the parent compound. Thus, by comparing the ν_{CO} values with those of the similar adducts^{9,19} and oxidised products, it can be suggested that in the adducts, $[\text{RhCl}(\text{CO})(\text{R}_2\text{S})_2\text{TCNE}]$, the metal ion is present in the +3 oxidation state and that the adducts have structure (B).

Electronic spectra : The uv-vis spectral data of a few oxidised products have been studied. The complexes, $[\text{RhClYZ}(\text{CO})(\text{R}_2\text{SO}/\text{R}_2\text{S})_2]$, where $\text{YZ}=\text{Br}_2$ and I_2 , exhibit three absorption bands in

the uv-vis region. The high energy bands occur in the region 36 000–39 000 cm^{-1} and the low energy absorption bands at 22 000–23 500 cm^{-1} . In octahedral complexes $[\text{RhClYZ}(\text{CO})(\text{R}_2\text{SO}/\text{R}_2\text{S})_2]$, the ligand molecules contain high energy empty π -orbitals which interact with the filled T_{2g} orbitals. The absorption bands in the visible region have been assigned²² as transitions from $^1A_{1g}$ ground state to $^1T_{1g}$ and $^1T_{2g}$ states.

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